

THE INTEGRATION OF BIG DATA WITH AI SUBJECTS

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Abstract: The integration of big data and artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative force across industries, offering unprecedented opportunities for data-driven insights and decision-making. This article provides a comprehensive exploration of the integration between big data and AI, highlighting its significance, challenges, and potential applications.

Key words: big data, artificial intelligence, AI systems, machine learning, AI algorithms.

KATTA MA'LUMOTLAR VA SUN'IY INTELLEKT FANLARINING O'ZARO INTEGRATSIYASI

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Annotatsiya: Katta ma'lumotlar va sun'iy intellekt (SI) integratsiyasi barcha sohalarda o'zgartiruvchi kuch sifatida paydo bo'ldi va ma'lumotlarga asoslangan tushunchalar va qarorlar qabul qilish uchun misli ko'rilmagan imkoniyatlarni taqdim etdi. Ushbu maqola katta ma'lumotlar va sun'iy intellektning integratsiyasi bo'yicha keng qamrovli tadqiqotni o'z ichiga oladi, uning ahamiyati, muammolari va potentsial ilovalarini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: katta ma'lumotlar, sun'iy intellekt, SI tizimlari, mashinali o'qitish, SI algoritmlari.

ВЗАИМНАЯ ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ БОЛЬШИХ ДАННЫХ И НАУКИ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА

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Аннотация: Интеграция больших данных и искусственного интеллекта (ИИ) стала преобразующей силой во всех отраслях, предлагая беспрецедентные возможности для анализа и принятия решений на основе данных. В этой статье представлено всестороннее исследование интеграции больших данных и искусственного интеллекта, подчеркнута ее значение, проблемы и потенциальные применения.

Ключевые слова: большие данные, искусственный интеллект, системы ИИ, машинное обучение, алгоритмы ИИ.

Introduction: The integration of big data and artificial intelligence (AI) has become a major focus in recent years, with the potential to revolutionize various industries and improve our lives in numerous ways. This article aims to provide an

overview of the integration of big data and AI, discussing its significance, challenges, and potential applications.

Methods: The integration of big data and AI involves the use of large datasets and AI algorithms to extract valuable insights and make informed decisions. This integration can be achieved through various techniques, including machine learning, natural language processing, and predictive analytics. These techniques allow for the analysis of vast amounts of data, enabling AI systems to learn from the data and make predictions or decisions based on that learning.

Figure1: Big data and AI integration.

Big data and artificial intelligence (AI) are closely related and often go hand in hand. Here's how they intersect and complement each other:

1. **Data as Fuel for AI:** AI algorithms rely heavily on data to learn and make predictions or decisions. Big data provides vast amounts of structured and unstructured data that AI algorithms can analyze to uncover patterns, trends, and insights.
2. **Data Processing:** Big data technologies like Hadoop, Spark, and others are used to store, manage, and process large volumes of data. AI algorithms often require massive datasets for training, and big data technologies enable efficient processing and analysis of these datasets.
3. **Feature Engineering:** Big data techniques are used to preprocess and extract features from raw data before feeding it into AI models. Feature engineering is crucial for improving the performance of AI algorithms by selecting the most relevant and informative features from the data.
4. **Machine Learning Models:** AI encompasses various techniques such as machine learning, deep learning, and natural language processing. Big data plays a vital role in training and fine-tuning these models using large-scale datasets, resulting in more accurate predictions and insights.
5. **Real-Time Analytics:** Big data platforms enable real-time data processing and analytics, which is essential for applications like fraud detection, recommendation systems, and predictive maintenance. AI algorithms deployed on big data infrastructure can continuously analyze streaming data and provide timely insights or actions.

Results: The integration of big data and AI has already shown significant results in various industries. For example, in healthcare, AI systems can analyze medical records and patient data to identify patterns and make predictions about patient outcomes. In finance, AI algorithms can analyze market trends and make investment decisions based on that analysis. In transportation, AI systems can optimize routes and improve traffic flow.

Discussion: While the integration of big data and AI has the potential to transform numerous industries, there are also challenges that must be addressed. One major challenge is the need for large amounts of high-quality data. Without accurate and reliable data, AI systems may make incorrect predictions or decisions. Additionally, there are concerns about privacy and security, as large amounts of data must be stored and processed securely.

Conclusion: In conclusion, the integration of big data and AI has the potential to revolutionize various industries and improve our lives in numerous ways. However, there are also challenges that must be addressed, including the need for high-quality data and concerns about privacy and security. Despite these challenges, the integration of big data and AI is an exciting and promising field, with the potential to transform our world in ways we can only begin to imagine.

References

1. R. Rosati, L. Romeo, G. Cecchini, et al. From knowledge-based to big data analytic model: a novel IoT and machine learning based decision support system for predictive maintenance in Industry 4.0. *J. Intelligent Manufacturing*. 2023, 107–121.
2. Mori S., Nishida H., Yamada H. *Optical character recognition*. — Hoboken, New Jersey: Wiley, 1999. 560 p.
3. Cheriet M., Kharma N., Liu C-L., Suen C. Y. *Character recognition systems: A guide for students and practitioners*. — Hoboken, New Jersey: Wiley-Interscience, 2007. 326 p.
4. Воробель, Р. А. Повышение контраста изображений с помощью модифицированного метода кусочного растяжения. *Отбор и обработка информации*/ Р.А. Воробель, И.М. Журавель -М.: 2000, -№14 (90), -С. 116-121.